

IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY FOR USING ENTREPRENEURIAL ACTIVITY IN IMPROVING THE WELL-BEING OF THE POPULATION

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Abstract. *In this article, the role of entrepreneurial activity in the economy of our country, the main areas of development of entrepreneurship, the scientific views of foreign and domestic scientists in this regard, the importance of entrepreneurship in improving the well-being of the population were studied as a result of analyzes. Based on the data, problems and shortcomings were identified and brought to them scientifically based conclusions and suggestions.*

Keywords: *population, entrepreneurship, development, economy, employment, population welfare, market, poverty, competition, tax, reform.*

СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ МЕТОДОЛОГИИ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ПРЕДПРИНИМАТЕЛЬСКОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ В ПОВЫШЕНИИ БЛАГОСОСТОЯНИЯ НАСЕЛЕНИЯ

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассмотрены роль предпринимательской деятельности в экономике нашей страны, основные направления развития предпринимательства, научные взгляды зарубежных и отечественных ученых на этот счет, значение предпринимательства в повышении благосостояния населения. популяции были изучены в результате анализов. На основе полученных данных были выявлены проблемы и недостатки и сделаны к ним научно обоснованные выводы и предложения.*

Ключевые слова: *население, предпринимательство, развитие, экономика, занятость, благосостояние населения, рынок, бедность, конкуренция, налог, реформа.*

Enter. Further development of entrepreneurial activities in the Republic of Uzbekistan the scope of the works carried out from year to year is increasing and, as a result, progress is being made in the development of the entrepreneurship sector, increasing its share in the economy is also increasing year by year. Human business and private business activity in its own way the market requires less financial resources quickly adapting to new conditions market requirements through identified opportunities Big business with faster fulfillment has priority over the activity. From this except business entities to market demand renewal of economic sectors as appropriate minimal resources during these activities consumption, has a positive effect on solving one of the permanent socio-economic problems - the issue of employment [1].

Currently, the main economic growth and economic development is the growth of gross domestic product as a factor, funds formed by subjects of entrepreneurship and economic activity is considered For this reason, the economic growth of the country cannot be imagined without the development of individual entrepreneurs and economic entities. "Entrepreneurship is the final result of the level of organization of business activity and the prosperity of the whole country with the growth of the national income level the conclusion "depends" is widespread.

Therefore, many factors influence the formation of entrepreneurial activity and its development is enough. In particular, the inclination of the society's ideology to entrepreneurship, this activity is state and public its use by institutions is of great importance.

Therefore, this society The attention of the government of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the activities of the Republic of Uzbekistan is increasing and further development of this field there is a need for theoretical justification.

Of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan By Decree No. PF-60 of January 28, 2022 approved for 2022-2026 Rapid development of the national economy and provision of high growth rates is envisaged[2]. The main goal of this course is to develop entrepreneurship is careful with.

Research methodology. Scientific research in the article comparative analysis, statistical analysis of data, improving the well-being of the population the importance of entrepreneurship, its methodology, ways of reducing poverty by involving the population in entrepreneurial activities were studied. Comparative analysis and analytical in our research work deepen the problem through the lines of analysis tried to learn. Problems are increasing given and in due order as his yeshiva giving conclusions and proposals, main directions passed. Uzbekistan as a research object entrepreneurial activity is taken as an example.

Analysis of literature on the topic. In his works, Y. Lowrey believes that "entrepreneurship is important for the economic well-being of the country." First, entrepreneurial jobs and gross domestic product (GDP) production that adds to the total value participation in the processes is a direction with production and entrepreneurial know-how. Secondly, entrepreneurship, the production of goods and services by whom and at what price the most efficient market to determine what you need creates an information system. Thus, entrepreneurs create a stable production environment, in which entrepreneurs take risks and constantly create new products and new markets technological progress with minimal costs can be provided [3].

Entrepreneurship by S. Lyubomirsky, K. Layous theory and researches show that entrepreneurs spend less money they begin to study market mechanisms. They operate out of market needs and consumer characteristics (e.g. their motivations and actions) and moderates their impact on consumer well-being. It also shows that entrepreneurship engenders four mediating variables: positive emotions, positive thoughts, positive behaviors, and need satisfaction. Empirical evidence supporting the model and they emphasize that it will be used to ensure the well-being of the population in the future [4].

A. Plyukhina the well-being of the population in the country ensuring the development of social entrepreneurship in improving the efficiency of promising social projects. Social entrepreneurs stimulation of socio-economic activity at different levels of the country's economy can be done. At the same time, that's it It should be noted that social entrepreneurs are only the welfare of the population in the country's economy so it serves. That is why it is social emphasizes the need to develop entrepreneurship [5].

According to V. Bessarabov, the level of economic security in the development of entrepreneurship assessment is important in the development of entrepreneurship serves as a factor. In evaluation, if the same financial statements that form the basis of the component in the title, as a rule, if objective, then other components He said that the analysis should be calculated subjectively or qualitatively. The main focus of his research is entrepreneurship ensuring the

economic security of its activities modern methods of developing entrepreneurship and ensuring the well-being of the population consists of analysis and integral assessment of its level [6].

A. Eraliyev: "...the future of entrepreneurship lies not only in the business environment, but also in society also to the level of development of entrepreneurial thinking reflecting the socio-economic situation depends. Economic to socio-economic situation independence, the class of entrepreneurs, the primacy of the market in economic relations, the accumulation of entrepreneurial capital and the use of necessary resources the existence of these conditions is included" [7], - brings.

Analysis and results. We have people in our country organization of activities of business and private business entities and their development through independent property owners class is forming. Quick adaptation of business activity to the requirements of the market economy importance with the breadth of possibilities earns. Therefore, ensuring the well-being of the population is the result of the development of business activities in our country The weight of this type of activity in GDP is from we can observe that it is increasing every year.

In the third quarter of 2023 compared to 2022 the share of entrepreneurship in the sectors has changed significantly. Share of entrepreneurship in GDP by 0.6%, its share in the industry decreased by 0.1% and on the contrary, its share in imports is 0.4%, in exports its share is 0.5%, its share in the construction sector is 2.7% showing an increase of %. So, entrepreneurs taking their activities more in the field of construction they prefer to go.

Personal business and private in our country through entrepreneurship development:

- a class of middle owners is formed;
- macroeconomic instability, unemployment and economic problems such as shortages are over finds;
- through the creation of a healthy competitive environment, GDP growth will be observed in terms of quantity and quality;
- business market with necessary goods (services) saturates and their quality increases;
- and ultimately, the population's standard of living will increase.

The development of human business and private entrepreneurship is not only in the development of the state and society, but also in the rise of every person important in meeting vital needs, i.e. service, retail trade, such as food production this activity is clearly manifested in the fields. At the same time, ensuring rapid growth of personal business and private entrepreneurship, private property protection, elimination of some administrative obstacles to the development of entrepreneurship, raising the quality of the investment and business environment in our republic to a new level fully meets international standards is reflected in provision.

The number of entrepreneurs in our country is increasing year by year. As just one example, in Q3 2023 compared to 2022, there were 8,374 or an increase of 17.1%. we can observe that new business entities are operating (**Table 1**).

Table 1

The number of registered business entities (in the cross-section of economic sectors)[8]

Classifier	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Agriculture, forestry and fisheries	19596	22062	25438	31098	43958	48854	57228
Mining and quarrying	1344	1556	1860	2427	2683	2886	3134
Manufacturing industry	42815	48053	55517	69733	83573	90936	99352
Construction	23536	25208	30305	37916	42905	45422	48828
Professional, scientific and technical activity	7516	8178	8940	10189	11850	12983	14394
Management activities and support rendering of service	6925	8706	9826	11603	13102	13455	15397
Arts, entertainment and recreation	1540	1908	2359	3098	3702	4246	4917
Provision of other types of services	4547	5283	5889	7622	9886	11260	13060
Supply of electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning	283	269	270	329	420	434	471
Water supply; sewage system, waste collection and disposal	897	863	1024	1142	1246	1292	1483
Information and communication	6681	6518	7130	8159	9877	10824	12510
Financial and insurance activities	4695	3966	3748	3657	3776	3297	3654
Transport and storage	11199	12287	13636	15881	17953	18867	21469
Accommodation and food services	16365	18037	20892	27243	32323	35261	39372
Wholesale and retail trade; motorized transport repair of vehicles and motorcycles	66497	66865	74604	106325	139545	165460	193492
Transactions with real estate	6066	6837	7187	7568	7884	8132	9096
Education	1250	1266	2133	3407	4484	6239	7800
Health and social services show	3800	4514	5477	6523	7813	9087	10313

Today, on the basis of the reforms carried out in our country, the state support and regulation of personal business and private entrepreneurship the mechanism can be explained as follows:

1. Reducing the influence of the state on the processes taking place in the economy, that is, regarding the procedures for granting permission by improving the mechanisms of state control transfer of some state functions to the private sector; of business structures with state participation pretending to be established; certain functions of state administration bodies, including replace them with alternative types of regulation; increase the volume of exports of local products, wide attraction of foreign investments, investment and tourist attractiveness of the country increase; activities such as the step-by-step transition to a new model of the economy specializing in the creation of advanced ideas, know-how and the development of "smart" technologies. As a result of this, due to the needs of exporting enterprises in the republic adoption of international standards, to the foreign market more than 2 thousand during the year in order to export quality and certified products introduction and certification of quality management systems in enterprises in accordance with international standards is envisaged.

2. Creating an environment of free competition, price stability and addressability of benefits to give up the practice of providing benefits individually in order to provide them, separate their production and service provision introduction of such types, that is, benefits in this setting conditions and criteria for granting, evaluating and monitoring their effectiveness implementation of the system; certain benefits subject to achieving a financial social result to give concessions on customs fees review; canceling the benefits on goods used in production, determination of acceptable duty payment rates; benefits not to individual subjects, but sectors or in relation to the types of goods (services, works) implementation is envisaged.

3. Residents and business entities increase confidence in the banking system, banks and effective between business entities and mutually beneficial cooperation relations provide.

4. Reducing and simplifying the tax burden, expanding production and the taxable base on this basis, that is, a new organization that is building such facilities unified tax on business entities the right to delay payment for a certain period to give it is envisaged to introduce a system of incentives for private enterprises to switch to payment of value added tax.

5. Support of entrepreneurial activity and improvement of business conditions the following is carried out, i.e. some control of the supervisory bodies functions of civil society institutions and transfer to state administration bodies; service of funds to business entities cash settlement in the sale of goods through information and communication technologies, in strict compliance with the collection rules at the leading banks, as well as products through international trading platforms using international payment cards simplification of the export system; legal any expenses related to the activities of production, trade, service, performance of work to individuals, including payments related to the payment of state duties and fees possibility to pay with corporate bank cards is implied; in the field of business activity licensing and permitting procedures reduction and simplification.

6. Entrepreneurship and innovation development of financing mechanisms for promising projects, that is, the legal status of venture funds and the procedure for their organization; venture companies and funds, venture regulating the activities of fund management companies and

innovative enterprises; venture companies and funds so qualified management and expert training of personnel and insurance of venture projects are provided. Social in places it is necessary to give priority to supporting business initiatives related to solving problems, especially youth and women's entrepreneurship. For this purpose, residents and entrepreneurs, microfinance services and financial resources, public procurement will be greatly expanded. To become an entrepreneur in the population through such programs passion and confidence increase, which means more income will strive to get.

In our opinion, personal business and private entrepreneurship should be further developed. In state support, special attention should be paid to:

firstly, effective use of logistics center services in exporting products of private business entities, i.e. quality development of marketing service and thereby ensuring the competitiveness of our national products in world markets;

secondly, development of exports based on the principle of "one lesson" for entrepreneurs and improvement of public service;

to encourage entrepreneurship and scientific research and innovative activities great attention should be paid. In this case, mutual (corporate) cooperation between the public and private business sectors based on cooperation, that is, wide and effective use of scientific achievements; entrepreneurship new innovative technologies in their activities use introduction of the most modern technologies in production; modernization of all branches and sectors of the national economy is important.

At the same time, increase the welfare of the population improvement of the methodology of using this business activity, economic, social and versatile, taking into account environmental factors takes the approach. In this context increase the efficiency of business activity Here are some strategies:

Development of social entrepreneurship, that is encouraging and supporting social entrepreneurship aimed at solving social problems in generating financial income. This can include businesses that address issues such as health, education, poverty and environmental sustainability.

Entrepreneurs of different origins through the development of inclusive entrepreneurship including women, minorities, and individuals from disadvantaged communities inclusiveness by providing opportunities promotion is meant. This is intended achieved through access to support programmes, mentoring and funding possible.

Training and skill development to equip individuals with the necessary entrepreneurial skills development of acquired education and skills invest in programs. This includes not only business skills, but also critical thinking, problem solving and adaptability. That's what entrepreneurs do, especially those who are in the early stages of their business funding should be improved. This includes the creation of microfinance programs, venture capital including the creation of funds or the development of innovative financing models adapted to the needs of entrepreneurs.

It is possible to stimulate entrepreneurship through the development of technology and innovation. It is necessary to develop an environment that encourages technological innovation. Research and development initiatives that lead to the creation of innovative products and services, economic growth and improved well-being support. Take advantage of networking opportunities,

mentoring programs, and co-working spaces supporting entrepreneurship it is necessary to create an ecosystem. It helps entrepreneurs connect with each other, share experiences and access valuable resources.

That's how to do business which reduces obstacles and is beneficial to entrepreneurs it is necessary to implement regulatory reforms that facilitate the start and development of businesses. This includes simplifying licensing processes, reducing bureaucratic obstacles, and creating a business-friendly environment also includes Encouraging ecologically sustainable entrepreneurship encouragement and support is also a motivating factor in the development of entrepreneurship is considered Economic development environment ensuring compatibility with protection such environmentally friendly practices and technologies acceptance should be facilitated.

It is necessary to assess the impact of business activity on the well-being of the population. That's why creation of monitoring and evaluation mechanisms is required. This is job creation, income will monitor key indicators such as level and community development. State and the development of cooperation between the private sector, public-private partnership for prosperity which has a wider and more stable effect creating initiatives of both sectors can use kushli sides.

Entrepreneurship in the economic crisis it is necessary to develop a strategy to increase the stability of its activity. These are emergency situations making plans, emergency funds can take on the task of providing access and support during difficult times. The world successful business models throughout as a result of the study, it can be said to facilitate the establishment of cooperation and exchange of knowledge in the prevention of crises. This in practice, to direct entrepreneurship to export and adapt them to the local context helps.

The effectiveness of these strategies may vary depending on the specific context, therefore, their entrepreneurial activities according to the type of adaptation to the needs of the community or region with business activities allows to engage.

Conclusions and suggestions. In conclusion in the economy of our country so that we can further raise the level of development, constantly improve the activities of personal business and private entrepreneurship, in our view, the following measures must be done:

Simplification of financing of personal business and private entrepreneurship activities in the regions and establishment of financial institutions development of their activities;

regions with a relatively low level of development development of special infrastructure development programs using these benefits and implementation;

wider involvement of representatives of this sector in the execution of state orders;

entrepreneurship in improving public welfare formation of new painting specialists;

extension of tax benefits to entrepreneurs by the state, etc.

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